

DOCUMENTATION PROCESSING IN THE SERVICE AT COASTAL FISHING PORT (CFP) PONDOKDADAP: APPLICATION OF THE RULES ON SERVICE COMPLIANCE

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Abstract

The enormous potential of Indonesia's seas complicates the utilization of its fisheries. Participating in illegal fishing and other forms of fisheries utilization violations continues to be prevalent among fisheries business actors, despite the fact that Indonesia has regulations and laws governing fishing businesses and fisheries. Data collection methods employed to ascertain the issues or conflicts that transpired included literature reviews, interviews with harbormaster officers, and observation. Harbormasters are one method by which fishing locations deal with difficulties. The fishing port has the authority to issue Sailing Approval Letters (SAL) to each fisherman in anticipation of this. The purpose of this study is to ascertain the regulations and laws governing the fishing industry, the jurisdiction and rationale for regulating the harbormasters authority, the sailing approval letter, and the existence of quantifiable captures as a means of safeguarding fisheries resources. The harbormaster is tasked with verifying the ship's documentation, including fishing license and Pass license is the Ship's National Marking Letter, and seaworthiness, with the understanding that each document is still legitimate. With respect to the finalized paperwork concerning the issuance of a declining SAL at CFP Pondokdadap. This decline was attributable to expired documents. Documents hold significant importance as they pertain to accountability for the safety of all elements, including the crew and the vessel. This is also associated with the implementation of Non-Tax State Revenue (NTSR) for fishermen; many fishermen continue to be confused by NTSR and are opposed to its existence. The same holds true for the regulation of measured fishing, which will subsequently be extended to encompass the quota allocated to individual business proprietors for fishing purposes.

Keywords: Fishing License, Fishing Business License, Fishing Vessel License, Sailing Approval Letter, Pododadap

INTRODUCTION

Exploiting Indonesian seafood is reprehensible given the scale of the country's enormous maritime potential. The irresponsible exploitation of Indonesian seafood typically involves unlawful capture, also known as illegal fishing. Illegal and unregulated fishing constitutes a significant challenge for the maritime environment of Indonesia (Saepullah & Noor, 2023). The high number of illegal fishing operations in the waters of Indonesia is a cause for serious concern. The consequences of illegal fishing in the waters of Indonesia have inflicted significant economic harm upon the nation. The repercussions of these losses are far-reaching and may pose a risk to the long-term viability of Indonesian marine resources and fisheries. In

cases where this negligent action fails to comply with the provisions outlined in Article 8 of Law of RI No. 31 of 2004.

Law of RI No. 45 of 2009 explicitly prohibits the use of materials that are detrimental to the environment and the long-term viability of fish resources within the fisheries management area of Indonesia (Ishak & Fatimah, 2019). In the face of irresponsible and non-compliant activities, the importance of supervision is to ensure that the government runs in accordance with the law. Additionally, it is capable of reacting to environmental-damaging activities, such as the exploitation of natural resources through fisheries. One of the principal means by which littoral communities acquire natural resources is through fishing (Efriyansah, 2016). The fishing resource exploitation activities in Indonesia are exceptionally vulnerable to conflict. Typical conflicts appear due to the utilization of unsuitable fishing equipment, the capture of fishing territories, and illegal fishing activities (Purnama et al., 2015). In addition to causing problems for the state, illegal fishing endangers the livelihoods of fishermen and fish producers (Magdalena & Sinaga, 2019). Fishing conflicts are additionally instigated by the substandard quality of fishermen, inadequate institutional capabilities to withstand surveillance, and a fishing deployment system that remains inadequate (Kusdiantoro et al., 2019). United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) 1982 regulates the resolution of hostilities. According to the established legal framework regarding territorial boundaries, a state's rights and obligations regarding its territorial territory are subject to the rule (Jamilah & Disemadi, 2020). Due to its close connection to illegal and unregulated fisheries, this legislation maintains strict enforcement. In Indonesia, overfishing is also associated with territorial territories. Due to the protracted reproduction period and inability to sustain continuous fish production (Liandi & Andryawan, 2022). The Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries Regulation No. Per.01/Men/2009 governs the 11 Fisheries Management Area (FMA) that define the boundaries of Indonesia's territory. The 11th division of the Indonesia's FMA is also adjusted to the fishing potential in the waters (Suman et al., 2017).

There are territorial boundaries in support of policies related to measured catches or quota-based and zoning-based catches. Measured fish catches are based on zoning, as management is related to the number of catches and restricted catch zones. Implementation to keep fish stocks awake (Cahyarani et al., 2023). This policy is intended to keep the marine ecosystem awake, but in terms of the economy, it's also balanced (Soumokit, 2022). This is because Indonesia has a fish species of 6.4 tons with a catch potential of 1.223.437 hectares. It's a huge and very encouraging figure to catch fish in Indonesian territory (Okatviardy et al., 2023). In support of government optimization of surveillance and other activities, as well as dealing with conflict. The Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries is authorized to develop fishing and maritime management of Indonesian marine wealth for the prosperity of the people and the country. The existence of non-tax state revenues (NTSR) is one of the main factors in the state's income, which comes from the payment of compensation for fishing permits. The implementation of NTSR is not only to preserve marine resources but also to improve the well-being of coastal communities in terms of development. (Daniarsyah, 2016). The city's role is also important in the process of reducing and preventing conflict. The municipality has authority in supervision in accordance with the provisions of the invitation law (Taufik et al.,

2016), whose functions and duties are set out in Law No. 17 Year 2008 on Shipping and Article 207 paragraph (1) that the municipality performs functions to the safety and safety of shipping, supervision and law enforcement, coercion, and protection of the environment. As for the role of a municipality in publishing SAL, A municipality publishes SAL regulated by Article 219 of Regulation No. 17 of 2008, which states that each vessel requires SAL or landing issued by the municipality so that the vessel can sail or land (Barus et al., 2017). This SAL is issued with some conditions that must be met by every vessel. These requirements are usually checked by the municipality at the local fishing port to see whether the vessel is able to sail. The police had previously carried out physical inspections and documentation of fishing vessels based on the measurement card, the vessel's national certificate, the safety certificate of the fisherman's vessel, the fishing license, and the license of a fishing enterprise. In completion of the inspection, harbormaster also carried out the competence inspection against the skipper or authority of the fishing vessel. Fishermen who have fulfilled the provisions will be given SAL to guarantee the safety and security of the vessel (Handoyo & Supriadi, 2021).

Based on the background above, it is important for fishermen to comply with the rules and laws in force. Therefore, this research is important to know the fishermen's compliance with the rules of navigation, the number of vessels that report to the administration in CFP Pondokdadap, as well as the legal basis for fishing and maritime, and the legal route of the fishing ports in the municipality of CFP. The optimization of navigation regulations relates to fishermen's compliance in carrying out measured catches and the acceptance of non-tax states in reducing illegal fishing. The purpose of this research is to find out the implementation of the laws and regulations of fishing, as well as the authorities of the municipality at the CFP Pondokdadap, the level of fishermen's compliance with the navigation administration that covers the issuance of SALs, meet the NTSR, and carry out the catch of measured fish at the CFP Pondokdadap, which aims to keep the fisheries resources kept awake sustainably. Related SAL publications in CFP Pondokdadap during July–September experienced a decline. In this case, the role of the overseer is to carry out inspections and remind the fishermen of the documents on the ship.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This research was conducted for 30 working days at CFP Pondokdadap, Malang of East Java Indonesia. Data was collected directly through interviews, direct observation in the field, and a desk study. Interviews were conducted with parties who are experts in their fields regarding fisheries regulations and the authority of harbormasters at fishing ports.

Figure 1: Research Location

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Law of Fisheries and Harbormaster

One of the problems that often arises is related to the continued depletion of fish resources. Therefore, there is a legal reference in the Law of RI No. 45 of 2009 that regulates the law of fishing. There are important things to bear in mind regarding the mandatory provisions for every person who engages in a business or activity in the management of fisheries. This law is designed to keep Indonesian marine fisheries resources under control in the areas of capture, cultivation, transportation, processing, and marketing in Indonesia. (Nainggolan et al., 2021). The exploitation of fishing resources has a clear legal basis. This law is contained in RI Law No. 45 of 2009, which contains a fisheries law. There are some important things that are contained in the contents of Law No. 45 of 2009, which is about mandatory provisions for every person who undertakes business or activities in the management of fisheries. UU No. 45 of 2009 serves to keep Indonesian marine fisheries resources under control in the areas of capture, cultivation, transportation, processing, and marketing in Indonesia. As an advocate for carrying out such activities, there is a form of license that must be completed for each fishing entrepreneur, such as fishing business license, fishing license, fishing vessel license, and SAL (Sihombing, 2017).

Regarding the exploitation of resources, fishing must be regulated to keep marine ecosystems sustainable. Other regulations that also deal with the legal rules governing the exploitation of fisheries resources are Law No. 6 of 2023 on the establishment of government regulation No. 2 of 2022 on the creation of work into law (Tarmizi et al., 2023). Article 26(1) states that any person engaged in fishing activities in the territory of the management of fishing of the State

of the Republic of Indonesia must have permission to do so from the central government or the district. The importance of a fishing license for prevention related to illegal fishing a vessel that does not have a fishing license is an act of theft against a fishery resource that does not report its catch to the local government. (Rudiansyah, 2016). The existence of permits allows the government to determine which parties are allowed to undertake business activities in the field of fishing. This license is also an effort to ensure the sustainability of fish resources and the construction of fishing enterprises to boost the development of the fishing world. It doesn't mean the freedom of an uncontrolled fishing entrepreneur to exploit the fishing resources (Mayangsari et al., 2016). There are many cases of violations of Indonesian fishing laws (Sasvia, 2019).

The Law No. 45 of 2009, which regulates the law of fishing, also regulates fishing activities. In Act No. 23 of 2014, which is discussed in more detail in Article 27, Paragraph (3), the authority of the province to manage fisheries resources in paragraph (1), capture activities must be carried out within a maximum distance of 12 miles from the coastline towards the open sea. Moreover, the law states that the provinces have maritime territory, whereas the districts have no marine territory (Marefanda & Djusfi, 2018). It is explained in Law No. 45 of 2009 that the fisheries management territory of the Republic of Indonesia includes fishing, Indonesian waters, and ZEE. This law supports the development of optimum fishery management territories in Indonesia as well as the sustainability of fish resources (Sarkol, 2017). Implementation and operational monitoring of capture in Indonesia are still lacking due to the size of the fishing management area (FMA), the minimum of facilities and supplies, and personnel (Tidajoh et al., 2020).

All activities in fishing ports, especially fishing enterprises, are required to have a fishing permit. Not only that, the fishing port also has a municipality for a technical and nautical inspection of the ship that helps in the process of fishing permits. The authority of the fishing municipality is regulated in CFP Permen No. 3 Year 2013 on fishing townships in fishing ports. The city has a basic foundation for every decision and has authority over it. The fishing port authority has the right to issue a sailing permit. It is regulated by Article 42, Paragraph 3, of Law No. 45 of 2009, which stipulates that every fishing vessel is required to have a license to sail before catching fish (Marzuki et al., 2023).

Sailing Approval Letter (SAL)

The Law of Fisheries and Harbormasters the authority to issue letters of voyage approval resides with the harbormaster officer at CFP Pondokdadap. To obtain SAL, fishermen must complete a number of procedures prior to fishing. It is comparable to organizing the departure of a vessel by completing the paperwork supplied by the service officer. The service officer examines the vessel's documentation, including the seaworthiness, fishing license, and PAS, while considering the active validity period of each document. The port of Monitoring Controlling and Surveillance (MCS) will receive a correspondence containing comprehensive information from the service officer regarding vessels that possess complete documentation and an active validity period. Subsequently, the MCS of the port will issue an operation eligible letter, a critical prerequisite for harbormasters to fulfill when issuing SALs. The port

harbormaster shall verify the crew's qualifications on the departing papers and reassess the active period of the vessel's documents. There are numerous crew alterations on the vessel that is about to depart compared to the previous voyage. The confirmation of this will be carried out by the port harbormaster for various crew members in order to determine the reason for the crew member change. This is to ensure the safety and security of the vessel's personnel while they are fishing. The port harbormaster will emphasize the signature as a significant responsibility in the concluding phase to ensure that the vessel is safe to sail. The harbormaster of the port issues a weather advisory to the crew of fishermen at the SAL. As stated in the advisory, fishing becomes hazardous during inclement weather; therefore, anglers ought to assess the forecast prior to venturing out. SAL issuance at CFP Pondokdadap is exceptionally challenging. Due to the fact that CFP Pondokdadap has only one harbormaster officer, it is not possible to inspect the safety apparatus and physical condition of the vessel in accordance with shipping procedures. Figure 2 is an illustration of the SAL that the CFP Pondokdadap harbormaster issued.

In order to monitor fishing vessels, there is a SAL that serves for safety on the sea. The process for the expenditure of SALs is carried out with the authority of the municipality of a fishing port. The municipality has very important authority over the physical inspection and documentation of fishing vessels, such as measurements, vessel national marks, safety certificates, fishing permits, and fishing business permits. The document is an important document that each vessel has as support for obtaining SAL. The municipality of a fishing port also has authority in determining the area of navigation of the vessel that has been designated and warning about the weather hazards while sailing. harbormaster conducted a physical inspection of the ship to issue a certificate of excellence and assess the ship's maintenance (Sitompul, 2016). SAL is an important document that every fisherman has because there is very clear evidence related to the readiness of ships that have been inspected by the harbormaster (Herman et al., 2023). As far as the law or criminal action against a fishing vessel that does not have SAL is concerned, it is considered illegal fishing. In this case, the arrest occurred because of the falsification of documents against SIPI and documents not matching the ship (Faisal et al., 2023). Related to this SAL problem is the need to enhance the role of the city through technical, nautical, and administrative skills. This increased role serves as a step to anticipate ships that do not have a complete letter, ships, goods, or the soul of the sea. (Suryani et al., 2018).

Figure 2: Sailing Approval Letter

Non-Tax State Revenue/NTSR (Pendapatan Negara Bukan Pajak/PNBP)

At CFP Pondokdadap, the harbormaster always reminds the heads of fishermen that NTSR will or may have been applied in some ports. Many fishermen still do not understand the NTSR, and many of the fishermen also feel objectionable to the existence of the NTSR. Fishermen assume that the NTSR is harmful to the fishers by paying fees to the central government of the catch fisheries that are obtained. Therefore, in the Pondokdaap application of the NTSR, there are still very few ships that implement this change. Even so far, at the CFP Pondokdadap, there are just two fishing boats that have moved permits to the center. The ship was from Sinai, but the ship had left the harbor of Pondokdadap and returned to Sinai.

At the moment, there are changes in the regulations for the navigation of fishing vessels, in particular the calculation of fish catch output. To report the catch, the fishermen directly report their catch to the central government, called the NTSR. In the NTSR process, the ship that sails directly permits access to the center. It is also a step in the development of the province funded by this NTSR. The NTSR is a penalty imposed against exploitation of catch fishing that can be called taxes (Samosir et al., 2014). In the case of a fishing enterprise, the size of the GT (gross-toned) of the vessel that is going to catch the fish is seen. In the event of the withdrawal of the GT of the fish, the result of the catch is based on the fixed target price (Sitepu et al., 2023). The withdrawal of the fishing enterprise is paid when the entrepreneur already has a permit for fishing marked with the presence of fishing business license or fishing license. In fact, the implementation of the NTSR in the field is very difficult. Many fishermen think the withdrawal of the NTSR is very detrimental to them. The money from the GNP (Gross National Product) would then go directly to the finance ministry. This GNP will be returned to the respective regions to help with the development of the region as well as the construction of a decent

fishing port. In Pondokdadap itself, there was a withdrawal of NTSR from the fishing output cut of 5%. This 5% can be seen in average ships with a gross tonnage of ships < 30 GT (Nainggolan et al., 2021). There is a NTSR as a measure to implement sustainable port development and fishing. Sustainable fishing will be projected as a measurable catch that can preserve fish resources.

Measurable Fishing

The implementation of measured fishing at CFP Pondokdadap is now starting to run. However, so far, this is massive in the evaluation stage of the various parties. Parties, specifically to the shipowner who has a self-employed business. The phase carried out in the CFP Pondokdadap is socialization for the shipowner related to the application of measured fish catch in the exploitation of fish resources. These measured fish catches will later be regulated in connection with the quota given to each business owner to catch fish. This step is an effort to reduce overfishing and sustain fish resources. The role of CFP Pondokdadap for the present in the application of measured fish catch in the evaluation phase of the activities of the vessel undertakings for 1 year all vessels that are going to catch measured fish must first undergo an independent effort evaluation.

The Indonesian people take advantage of its vast marine wealth. In ecosystems and the availability of existing fish, there are many ways to obtain fish and other marine resources. The measured catch policy is made in Indonesia, one of which, in Article 27 of 2021, describes the division of territory in the Fisheries Management Area of the Republic of Indonesia (FMARI). FMARI is the division or region of management for the catch of fish in the waters of Indonesia. This division is carried out in order to optimize the management of sustainable fisheries resources. In Indonesia, FMARI is divided into 11 regions for the management of fishing. FMARI is an optimization for the prevention of IUU fishing and overfishing. Pathway in the establishment of management territory and the creation of direct fisheries by the presidential decree No. 15 of 2015 on fisheries illegal fishing The number of illegal fishermen, along with various breaches of regulations and other laws (Chapsos & Hamilton, 2019). The existence of this FMARI in support of sustainable fisheries management is also supported by government regulations related to catch allocation, estimates of fish potential, and the number of allowed catches. This will make the catch controlled and balanced according to the zone. The difficulty in this application is the fisherman's lack of knowledge related to the location of potential catch (Syetiawan, 2016). The catch is measured as a rule in the catch of fish according to the cotta that is caught according to its need. The policy on measured fishing is a reform of the management of fisheries that is filled with output control with quota allocation for fishermen, non-commercial quotas, and for industry (Sadir et al., 2023). The disadvantage of measured fish catch is considered to be small-scale fishermen's fishing with entrepreneurs, who make it difficult for traditional fishermen to find fish in the sea. The division of the FMARI on fishing is very concerned with making it easier for foreign investors to build a business and forgetting the protection against small fishers (Pratiwi et al., 2022).

Persentase of SAL published in UPT Pondokdadap for 3 months

CFP Pondokdadap through the authorized port authority in the publication SAL. SAL is very important for every fisherman to have as proof of license for fishing activities. In this study, we obtained the presence of a percentage of SAL issued by the port authorities to see the decrease in SAL publication that exists in the CFP Pondokdadap. This figure was seen for 3 months in the months of July–September 2023 (Figure 3).

Figure 3: SAL publication during the month of July-September

Based on Figure 3, there was a significant decrease in SAL publication in CFP Pondokdadap in July–September 2023. In July, 66 SALs were issued by the CFP Pondokdadap for fishermen with a size of 11–29 GT. The catch devices used are the ulur pancing and the hand line of tuna. The CFP Pondokdadap has a catch area, or FMARI, of FMARI 573 (Route I). The catch output in August was 940 kg–5.650 kg.

Causes of decline in SAL publications from July to September

There was a decrease in the publication of SALs in the CFP Pondokdadap from July to September. The results of data collection with interviews say that fishermen's compliance with the rules is 10%. This is due to the large number of documents on the ship that have expired. This has resulted in many fishermen who have not or have not extended their documents. The problem arises because fishermen consider a document to be irrelevant because, without it, they can still catch fish. Another reason for the decrease in the issuance of SALs is the number of documents that have expired due to the lack of officials on the field. The source also explains that the SAL's conditions are issued when the document is still active at the time of its validity. The other problem in the field is the communication between officers and fishermen, which is often wrong. The communication problem occurs like a fisherman who feels that he has the

documentation and the results of their capture for the officer, but at the time of the inspection, it turns out that he does not have the documents or the catch. While carrying out the loading activities, some fishermen left their documents, and the fisherman didn't report the catch. While taking care of the departure, some fishermen will look for documents that have been left before. In the field, they also captured a lot of ships that did not have SAL. This action is very unfortunate because it will later affect the fishermen themselves, both in terms of safety and legal permits associated with the catch. It is very important that the SAL be carried by the fishermen as proof that the catches have a catch permit in the designated area.

Navigating documents has relationships between one document and the other. In strict ports, fishermen who do not have SAL will not be lifted, and there are strict sanctions and fines. However, it can be seen that the content of this document has an influence on the process of exporting the capture. Related to the export of catches, each country has different regulations. Especially in countries of the European Union that are very strict in document checks. In the case of undocumented or incomplete catches, it is considered a fishing IUU for a country of the European Union. The fish to be exported must have an SHTI (fish catch certificate) with a derivative sheet. SHTI obtained with the initial step of obtaining LA (Prime Sheet). LA (Premise Sheet) is a letter of attestation that fills in the information of all catches regulated in PERMEN KP 10 Year 2021. LA (Premium Sheets) that have been obtained publish SHTI in 2 forms, namely SHTI-LT with a medium and large scale and SHTI-LTS with a micro scale with a small range of 5–20 GT. The final stage is the issuance of a processing declaration, which is a declaration that the products are exported to the European Union using raw materials from other countries that have already identified a catch certificate for the EU.

Solution To The Problem

On the issue of falling SAL published from July to September, there must be optimal measures related to this. It's about an expired document that needs to be extended. From the analysis obtained, there must be strong action against the extension of this document. The extended document will affect the publication of the SAL issued by the Port Authority. There must be enforcement of the rules on the ground against the arrest ban until the document is extended. The document not only deals with administrations to be complied with, but it also affects the fishing vessel's official conduct of fishing in the Indonesian Sea. The document also deals with the responsibility for the safety of the entire component, whether it is a ship or an abbey of a ship.

Basically, there are still many obstacles to the conflict that has occurred in fishing exploitation. Law enforcement doesn't work properly. The lack of law enforcement has led to various violations of the law in Indonesian maritime territory. Let the law enforcement in the sea be done by one authority, so that there is no overlap of authority in the law enforcement (Zhuo et al., 2020). In the implementation of policy, it needs socialisation and good communication. Effective communication must come consistently and clearly from the authorities (Mandala et al., 2016). Implementation of policies that take place in other areas, like the sibolga, requires serious legal action. The action of the government of the Sibolga region against catch fishing is surveillance, with monitoring and reporting on certain violations. Synergy between TNI AL,

the Water Police, and the Maritime and Fisheries Service in the surveillance of marine resources and fishing, as well as PSDKP's role in forming a monitoring post in the fisheries management area. The other measure is the withdrawal of a licence to sail for a vessel that does not have a complete document. The other action is the arrest of the vessel by TNI AL and the Water Police. This action is a legal action in the implementation of public legal action, which must be subject to the provisions of public law in the field of fishing and maritime sources of the laws. The main thing to solve the problem that has arisen is the importance of continuously raising public awareness and the use of resources (Zaki, 2018). The involvement of stakeholders also needs to anticipate the challenges facing local fishermen related to the implementation of policy in the problematic fish expo zone (Darmasetiadi et al., 2023).

CONCLUSION

In the Act No. 45 of 2009 on fisheries which establishes mandatory provisions for every person who engages in business or activities in the management of fisheries. The Act also regulates Indonesia's marine fisheries resources to be controlled in the area of capture, cultivation, transportation, processing, and marketing, as well as the territory of fisheries management of the Republic of Indonesia including fishing, and regulates the related obligation to have a sailing license. SAL published by the port authorities regulated in the CCP Cake No. 3 Year 2013 on the municipality in fishing ports. Harbormaster will re-check on the active time of the ship's documents and perform a check on the compatibility of the vessel's crew as there are frequent changes to the crew of vessels that will depart from the previous departure.

In taking care of the fisherman's documents to carry out the catch, there are some procedures to be done. The procedure is like taking care of the departure of the ship by filling in the paper already provided by the service officer. During the departure of the ship, officers checked the ship's documents, such as the vessel's identity, fishing license, and large PAS, taking into account any documents that were still active at the time of their validity. Active documents and obtaining SAL are allowed to carry out arrest, but for now there are post-arrest regulations namely NTSR (State Non-tax Acceptance) that are applied in CFP Pondokdadap. The implementation of the NTSR has not been able to go well because the fishermen's understanding of this policy is still very poor. Another policy adoption is related to quota-based measured fishing. At the CFP Pondokdadap for the current in the application of measured fish catch in the evaluation phase of the activities of the ship enterprise for 1 year. This is aimed at sustainable fisheries management and conservation of fisheries resources.

Related to all the activities carried out on the service in CFP Pondokdadap, on one of the activities is the publication of SAL. It was obtained that in July there were 66 SAL, August 51 SAL and September 13 SAL that were issued. There has been a decline in the process of issuing SALs at the CFP Pondokdadap due to the large number of ship documents that have expired. However, it can be seen that the completion of this document will also make it easier in the export process.

Declaration of Interest Statement

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